

Function $f(n+6)$

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Abstract :

The particular progression relation of this function $n + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6 + 6.....$ generates successively prime and composite numbers which are connected to the next and previous function $f(n + 6)$

This Function $f(n + 6)$:

$$f(n + 6) = (n^2 - 1 * (4 * n + 5)) = N$$

$$\frac{N}{n+1} =$$

odd integer prime number or composite number

Example:

$$n = 6$$

$$f(n) = N = 7$$

$$factor = 7 = 1 * 7$$

$$NOTE : \frac{N}{n+1} = \frac{7}{6+1} = 1$$

$$n = 12$$

$$f(n) = 91$$

$$factor = 91 = 1 * 7 * 13$$

$$NOTE : \frac{N}{n+1} = \frac{91}{12+1} = 7$$

$$n = 18$$

$$f(n) = 247$$

$$factor = 247 = 1 * 13 * 19$$

$$NOTE : \frac{N}{n+1} = \frac{247}{18+1} = 13$$

$$n = 24$$

$$f(n) = 475$$

$$factor = 475 = 1 * 5 * 5 * 19$$

$$NOTE : \frac{N}{n+1} = \frac{475}{24+1} = 19$$

$$n = 30$$

$$f(n) = 775$$

$$factor = 775 = 1 * 5 * 5 * 31$$

$$NOTE : \frac{N}{n+1} = \frac{775}{30+1} = 25$$

$$n = 36$$

$$f(n) = 1147$$

$$factor = 1147 = 1 * 31 * 37$$

$$NOTE : \frac{N}{n+1} = \frac{1147}{36+1} = 31$$

$$n = 42$$

$$f(n) = 1591$$

$$factor = 1591 = 1 * 37 * 43$$

$$NOTE : \frac{N}{n+1} = \frac{1591}{42+1} = 37$$

$$n = 48$$

$$f(n) = 2107$$

$$factor = 2107 = 1 * 7 * 7 * 43$$

$$NOTE : \frac{N}{n+1} = \frac{2107}{48+1} = 43$$

$$n = 54$$

$$f(n) = 2695$$

$$factor = 2695 = 1 * 5 * 7 * 7 * 11$$

$$NOTE : \frac{N}{n+1} = \frac{2695}{54+1} = 49$$

$$n = 60$$

$$f(n) = 3355$$

$$factor = 3355 = 1 * 5 * 11 * 61$$

$$NOTE : \frac{N}{n+1} = \frac{3355}{60+1} = 55$$

$$n = 66$$

$$f(n) = 4087$$

$$factor = 4087 = 1 * 61 * 67$$

$$NOTE : \frac{N}{n+1} = \frac{4087}{66+1} = 61$$

$$n = 72$$

$$f(n) = 4891$$

$$\text{factor} = 4891 = 1 * 67 * 73$$

$$\text{NOTE : } \frac{N}{n+1} = \frac{4891}{72+1} = 67$$

$$n = 78$$

$$f(n) = 5767$$

$$\text{factor} = 5767 = 1 * 73 * 79$$

$$\text{NOTE : } \frac{N}{n+1} = \frac{5767}{78+1} = 73$$

$$n = 84$$

$$f(n) = 6715$$

$$\text{factor} = 6715 = 1 * 5 * 17 * 79$$

$$\text{NOTE : } \frac{N}{n+1} = \frac{6715}{84+1} = 79$$

$$n = 90$$

$$f(n) = 7735$$

$$\text{factor} = 7735 = 1 * 5 * 7 * 13 * 17$$

$$\text{NOTE : } \frac{N}{n+1} = \frac{7735}{90+1} = 85$$

$$n = 96$$

$$f(n) = 8827$$

$$\text{factor} = 8827 = 1 * 7 * 13 * 97$$

NOTE : $\frac{N}{n+1} = \frac{8827}{96+1} = 91$

Conclusions :

Update soon